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THE UNIQUE ROLE OF THE NATURAL RESOURCES OF THE NAKHCHIVAN AUTONOMOUS REPUBLIC AZERBAIJAN IN THE HUMAN BODY

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Abstract

The article is dedicated to the unique role of the natural resources of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic in the human body. Here, the mechanism of influence of natural healing places in Nakhchivan and the flora of Nakhchivan's climate on the pathologies occurring in the human body is determined and the effectiveness of treatments is determined.

Keywords: health, treatment, disease, pathology, medicine, frost. Access and Research area

Duzdag physiotherapy center is located at an altitude of 1173 m above sea level. In 2006, during the reconstruction works carried out in the underground department of the hospital, conditions were created in accordance with the most modern requirements. The center can receive 350 patients at the same time. As we know, this type of treatment centers exist in many countries such as Ukraine, Poland, Kyrgyzstan, Germany. However, due to its several advantages, the Duzdag Physiotherapy Center in Nakhchivan has no analogues.

Daridag thermal water with arsenic, which is 15 kilometers northeast of Julfa region, has therapeutic value for many skin diseases such as scabies, jaundice, pyoderma. To treat those diseases, you should take a bath in Daridag water. The duration of the treatment sessions is in the territory of Babek district, 6 kilometers southeast of the village of Gahab, 12 kilometers from the city of Nakhchivan, at the foot of the Ashabi-Kahf mountain. It boils and foams every 15 minutes. The water is radon, carbon dioxide, slightly mineralized, hydrocarbonate-chlorine-sulfate, sodium-calcium. It is an analogue of "Pyatigorsk" water in the Russian Federation. It is used in the treatment of rheumatism. It is different depending on the type and degree of severity. Being a window to the past from all parts of this beautiful land, Nakhchivan is developing and preserving its antiquity. This land, which lives history with

its ancient cultural and historical monuments, is also a place of healing. Nakhchivan has its own nature and terrain [Kakhramanov S.G., 1984 p. 58-83; Kakhramanov S.G., 1989, p. 56-60; Feyruz Bagirov? 2008, p. 26-101].

"DUZDAĞ" Physiotherapy Center is a unique salt cave where you can get full health as a drug-free treatment. According to the World Health Organization, approximately 10 percent of the world's population suffers from allergic diseases, of which 1.5-2 percent is bronchial asthma. According to information, about 15 million people in the world suffer from bronchial asthma. Bronchial asthma is an allergic, chronic disease characterized by increased secretion in the bronchi, edema of the mucous membrane of the bronchi, spasm of the bronchial muscles, and suffocation after these cases, depending on various etiological factors. In the treatment of many diseases, as well as bronchial asthma, the treatment carried out under the conditions of salt frost, that is, spleotherapy, is more effective. "Spleotherapy" comes from the Greek "Spelaion" - cave, kaha and "therapia" - treatment. Nakhchivan MR Duzdag Physiotherapy healing center's advantage over other salt mines is that, since the mine is located horizontally, the patients enter the underground part with adaptation [Rzaev B.Z, 2012, p. 29-58; Rzaev BZ, Karaev A., 2013, p. 404]. Also, ventilation is natural in

the cold ,microbial bodies are low, allergens are absent.The humidity and temperature in the cave always

remain constant.The microclimate of the underground department is shown below:

Altitude above sea level	1173m
Temperature	18-20°
Atmospheric pressure	740 mm.c.st
Relative humidity	24-50%
Air speed	0-0,1m/s
Highly dispersed	Na ⁺ ,Cl ⁻ ionları
When not sick	17,5mq/m3
Oxygen	20%
Noise	15-20 DB
The composition of Duzdag salt	NaCl-98,4% ; CaCl-0,04% MgCl-0,06 %-dir.

There are 17-21 mg of sodium chloride ions in 1 cubic centimeter of air in the Duzdag mine.Since sodium and chlorine ions predominate, it has a very positive effect on the treatment of pleural bronchial diseases. They kind of disinfect the air and calm seizures.

After completion of treatment, 65-70% of adults and 80-85% of children improve.

Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, which is one of the ancient settlements, is very rich in mineral waters. Even this land can be presented as a museum of natural and mineral waters of the world.

The number of mineral water sources in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic is 225, and several of them are currently intensively used.

Most of the sources of these mineral waters, or rather most of them, are located in the valleys of Nakhchivanchay, Alinchachay, Gilanchay, Ordubadchay, Aylis rivers and near them.These mineral waters are diverse and colorful according to their chemical composition. They are used both as table and healing water.It should also be noted that the healing waters of the region have different compositions.Many of them are considered rare waters due to their composition.

The richness of the nature of Nakhchivan lies in the fact that even if these waters come from a close distance from each other, their composition and temperature differ significantly. You need to be an expert to tell that the spring that comes out of the ground in the creek near the small waterfall in the Shorsu creek, the springs that come out of the cracks in the rocks on both sides of the creek two to three meters away, and the non-aerated spring that comes out at a relatively high place, 4-5 meters away from them, are different from both of them. There is no. 300-400 meters east of the waterfall, the mineral water that comes out naturally from the rock crack has been used for treatment since ancient times.

People who see the benefit of these waters in the treatment of gastrointestinal and skin diseases and joint pains come here from long distances.Mineral waters such as Badamli Sirab, Gahab, Vaykhyr, Kyzylburun, and Daridag are very famous for their therapeutic value. For example, "Sirab-12" is a low-mineralized, cold, carbonated and hydro-carbonated mineral water. "Vaykhyr-7" mineral water is mostly used for chronic stomach and other diseases [Sefarly Babayev, 1999, p. 48-105].

The healing properties of mineral waters are determined by the 6 main ions in their composition – sodium, calcium, magnesium, chlorine, sulfate and hy-

drocarbonate.The diversity of water composition depends on the combination of these six elements in different proportions.

"Ashabi-kahf" mineral water of Nakhchivan is rich in radon. This water is similar to the famous Pyatigorsk (North Caucasus) water and is very effective in the treatment of nervous, cardiovascular and rheumatism diseases.

According to their chemical composition, almond water is mainly carbonic acid-hydrocarbonate-sodium, chloride-calcium.Their therapeutic value has been studied and it has been determined that "Badamli" water has a positive effect on liver and gall bladder diseases, and its therapeutic properties are similar to the properties of "Narzan" waters from Kislovodsk (North Caucasus).

One of the healing natural sources in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic is the Daridag Arsenic Water Treatment Plant, which is an underground resource with a large flow.

The investigation of "Darydag" healing water, distinguished by its specific properties, was carried out as early as 1830 by G. Boskoboynikov, in 1868 by Arkhilov and Sulkidze, and in 1928, along with the geological discovery of the water, Langvagren also studied its chemical composition.The chemical, physical, balneological, therapeutic and other properties of "Darydag" water are still being studied.

Daridag Arsenic Water Treatment Plant consists of 32 exploration wells and 5 springs.Comprehensive facilities for examination, treatment and relaxation of patients have been created in the clinic with examination rooms and indoor swimming pools.

. Arsenic water from spring No. 5, which comes from a depth of 1080 meters, is transported through pipes to separate closed pools.The temperature of the water in the spring is 52 degrees, in the baths it is 37-41 degrees. Here, ambulatory treatment of rheumatic, skin, muscle, nervous and musculoskeletal diseases is carried out by taking an arsenic water bath.The duration of treatment is 10-12 minutes a day for 12-14 days.

"Darydag" water with carbon dioxide, murky, highly mineralized chlorinated-hydrocarbonate, sodium is similar to the waters of Kudova (Poland), Durkheim (Germany), Sinegorsk (Sakhalin). However, due to the proportion of mineral salts in the water, "Darydag" water is superior to them.However, due to the proportion of mineral salts in the water, "Darydag" water is superior to them.

There is no such tissue, organ and system in the human body that this water does not restore its ability

to work by having a healing effect on it, improves the morphological composition of peripheral blood by having a positive effect on the activity of blood circulation organs - increases the phagocytosis ability of leukocytes, eliminates anemia. It activates the internal excretory system, normalizes the functional state of the stomach, liver, kidney and heart muscles by strengthening the autonomic nervous activity. Due to these properties, "Darydag" water is widely used in the treatment of stomach, gall bladder, liver and other diseases related to the autonomic nervous system. Many scientists who studied the effect of "Darydag" water on metabolism proved its therapeutic effect against arthritis caused by metabolic disorders. Doctors associate the quick cleaning of wounds from dirt, short-term and scar-free healing of hard-to-heal wounds with its anti-septic, phagocytic, and bactericidal abilities. It has been determined that the combined effect of marigold with lithium, bromine, magnesium, radioactive elements and other important substances has a positive effect on the recovery of metabolism and the activation of the peripheral nervous system. The duration of a specified session should not exceed 10-12 minutes for patients treated in "Darydag" arsenic hot water. Otherwise, expansion of cardiovascular vessels will occur.

Since ancient times, "Darydag" water has been widely used in the treatment of bone: joint, muscle system diseases, including pathologies called "salting" and its various complications [Kakhramanov S.G., 1984 p. 58-63].

"Daridag" plays an important role in restoring the health of the citizens of the country as well as those from foreign countries. Those who come to the clinic are served in all seasons of the year, all days of the week. Citizens of Turkey, Iran, Russia, Japan, Kazakhstan, etc. Are among those who use the services of the Daridag Arsenic Water Treatment Plant. The fact that Nakhchivan MR has a sharp continental climate, where there is little precipitation, dry weather, summer and autumn months are partly rainless and hot, cold winter, high temperature amplitude difference between days and seasons, affected the formation of the vegetation cover, and it is poorly uniform. That is, it led to the development of xerophytic plants. In the autonomous republic, medicinal plants are notable for their variety and abundance. It is important to have information about the rare and medicinally important plants of Nakhchivan.

Some of the common medicinal plants in Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic: Shatara, which is known as *Fumaria* in science and has 60 species, is known as shatara in the Ordubad dialect, and shatara in the Sharur dialect. This plant, which is listed in the "Red Book" of the world, is more common in hot and arid regions, and the climate of Nakhchivan is also suitable for shatara. It is an annual plant with many leaves, small, white, purple or pink flowers. The most important medicinal plant (*Fumaria officinalis*) grows in our country. Shatara (*Fumaria officinalis*) is a medicinal plant 20-60 centimeters tall. The plant contains tannin, sugar, fumarin and fumaric acid. This is important in the treatment of many diseases. It is used to treat gallbladder problems by increasing gallbladder secre-

tions. It can be used in case of itching, which has therapeutic effect on skin diseases. Effective results can be obtained when used in the treatment of vascular stiffness and liver. When used in appropriate doses, it helps to relieve stomach pain complaints. It also plays an important role in the treatment of diseases such as psoriasis, eczema, and hemorrhoids. It can be used to treat acne on the face and body. More attention should be paid to the research of this plant, which has a high therapeutic value, and conditions should be created for its wide use in medicine. *Achillea millefolium*, known by the scientific name *Achillea millefolium*, is an official medicinal plant included in the pharmacopoeia. The plant, whose aerial parts and flowers are used, is also used as an ore and infusion. The plant, which is widely used in scientific, experimental and folk medicine, as well as in clinical trials, has antioxidant, anthelmintic, hemostatic, expectorant, analgesic, antipyretic, antipyretic, spasmolytic and cardiostimulant effects. These effects play a fundamental role in the treatment of stomach, heart, kidney and kidney stones, bladder, bronchial asthma, skin, liver diseases, pulmonary tuberculosis, neurosis, colds, malaria, women, rheumatism, stomatitis, allergies, atherosclerosis and malignant tumors.

Along with these, it has a positive effect on the nervous system. After drinking Boimadaran tea, the general emotional state improves, depression, neurosis, stress and excessive tension are eliminated. It also plays an important role in cleaning the skin, increasing its elasticity and firmness, as well as strengthening the scalp and nails. It is not recommended to use the plant, which has a strong effect, during pregnancy.

Another rare medicinal plant, known scientifically as "Echinopsilon", is a mountain flower with gray-yellow-green colored flowers, round shape, dense leaves, and from a distance it looks like mountain stones. It mostly grows in the high mountains of Ordubad, Shahbuz, Kangarli, Babek and Sadarak regions. The flowering period is from June to August and attracts insects. It is not eaten by animals. In folk medicine, special ointment (balm) is prepared from leaves and flowers. A type of tis-tis plant, the tis-tis plant is surrounded by small flowers that look like a hedgehog and are spiky.

It is spread on the mountain slopes of most regions of the Autonomous Republic, which also has therapeutic value.

The *Astragalus* plant is common in the Ordubad, Julfa, Shahbuz regions of the Autonomous Republic on the high mountain slopes (in the north). In folk medicine, the plant, whose flowers and leaves are brewed against cardiovascular diseases, is in danger of extinction because it was collected by the population in the 70s and 80s. In all regions of the Autonomous Republic, in particular, *Euphorbia*, another medicinal plant that is widespread in the plain-meadow areas, is widely used in folk medicine. Since the flower, leaves and stem of the plant contain a poisonous substance (a sticky milky liquid), only its roots are used.

- *Centaurium* is a perennial grass plant from the family of flowering plants, which is common in the foothill meadows all over the world. *Centarium* pul-

chellum and Centarium umbellatum species of the medicinal plant are widespread in Azerbaijan (Nakhchivan MR).

- Capsella is a biennial herb from the Cruciferae family, distributed in the temperate zones of the world. In Azerbaijan (in Nakhchivan MR) there is only one species of the plant, the common bursa (Capsella bursa pastoris).

- Ginseng (Panax Ginseng) is a perennial herb from the ivy family. The ginseng plant was brought to the Zagatala territories of Azerbaijan in Khabarovsk region (Russia) in 1953. A similar species of this valuable plant is common in the Greater Caucasus and the Salvarti Plateau in the Autonomous Republic of Azerbaijan. Unfortunately, the plant is destroyed by carelessness during mowing and cannot complete the vegetation period.

- Horsetail (Afctium) is a perennial herbaceous plant belonging to the Angiospermaceae family. There are 4 types of plants in Azerbaijan (2 types in Nakhchivan MR). Medicinal plants common in the territories of Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic are used in the treatment of the following diseases;

- In the treatment of central nervous system diseases, catnip (Valeriana officinalis l.), ginseng (Panax Ginseng), etc.

- Adonis vernalis l., hawthorn (Crataegus), etc. Are used in the treatment of cardiovascular diseases.

- In the treatment of spasmolytic and painful diseases, lady's wort (Atropa belladonna l.), bat (Hyoscyamus niger l.), thyme (Thymus vulgaris), mint (Mentha piperita), fennel (Anethum graveolens), etc.

- Althae officinalis, juniper (Juniperus), licorice (Gtycyrrhiza gtabra l.), andiz (Znula), etc. Are used in the treatment of respiratory diseases.

- In the treatment of gastro-intestinal diseases, taraxacum (Taraxacum), plantain (Plantago), tea tree (Hippophae rhamnoides l.), sunflower (Helianthus annuus), cabbage (Brassica oleracea), etc.

- In the treatment of liver, gall bladder, kidney and urinary tract diseases, buckthorn (Fanacetum), barberry (Berberis vulgaris), corn (Zea maus), rose hips (Rosa caninal), etc.

- Nettle (Urtica l.), thistle (Berberis vulgaris), capsella (Capsella), chaytica (Hippophae rhamnoides l.), etc. Are used in the treatment of blood clots and internal bleeding.

- In the treatment of skin diseases, hypericum (Hypericum l.), juniper (Juniperus), onion (Allium cepa), garlic (Allium sativum), etc.

- Pumpkin seed (Cucurbita maxima), thyme (Thymus vulgaris), tarragon (Fanacetum), etc. Against intestinal worms.

- Antiseptic and cold-fighting thyme (Thymus vulgaris), sumac (Rhus coriaria), almond (Amygdalis comamunis), gooseberry (Solanum), etc.

- In the treatment of eye diseases, sumac (Rhus coriaria), pomegranate (Punica granatum), black tree fruits (Ulmus), etc.

It is our duty to deeply study these precious and rare resources that God has given us and protect our health.

Conclusion and suggestions:

The presence of natural healing resources of Nakhchivan, which is an ancient human and cultural abode, a museum of natural resources, called the "Gate of the East", leads to the development of great tourism potential. The peculiarities of the nature of Nakhchivan create ample opportunities for the development of medical tourism in this land. In this regard, Duzdag Physiotherapy Center has been known as a different treatment center not only in Azerbaijan, but also in our country for many years and increases the attractiveness of the autonomous republic for tourists. Environmentally clean air, abundance of solar radiation, as well as abundance of natural mineral waters have a significant impact on the development of health tourism in Nakhchivan.

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